

Fast fashion does not save you money

What is fast fashion?

Fast fashion is the term used to describe clothing designs that move quickly from the catwalk to stores to take advantage of trends. The affordability of fast fashion makes it possible for mainstream consumers to purchase the latest hot look or the next big thing. Fast fashion became common because of cheaper and faster manufacturing and shipping methods, an increase in consumer demand for the latest trends, and purchasing power to satisfy these instant gratification desires. It's not uncommon for fast-fashion retailers to introduce new products multiple times in a week to stay on trend.

Fast fashion is also called disposable fashion because it encourages a throw away consumer mentality. Fast fashionistas in their teens and early twenties, admit that they only wear their purchases once or twice as said by [Adam Hayes, 2023 from Investopedia](#).

Even if the clothes are affordable, that doesn't mean they're cheap and of good quality. It was said that *Shein* clothes (said to be the worst of all the fast fashion brands) only had a lifespan of no more than 10 uses before becoming unusable and ending up as landfill waste, according to [Nandini Sood 2022 from The Issue Magazine](#). Of course, not all fast fashion brands are like this; some clothes can last for quite a while, depending on how many times you use them or how good you are at taking care of them.

Fun Fact: Some people have allergic reactions to the synthetic chemicals in the clothes used to reduce cost. Not only that, but there have been claims that a lot of fast fashion brands have workers in inhumane working conditions, mostly being paid minimum wage or below it.

Some people might argue that they'd rather buy more clothes for less than fewer pricier clothes, for example, buying 50 items for \$200 than 5 items for \$200. It is fine if people think this way since some clothes are actually decent quality, though most of the time people throw clothes away when they don't like them anymore or just never use them any more after a few uses.

I'm not saying that you shouldn't buy fast fashion clothes, but if you're only doing it to follow trends, then your wallet will suffer since trends change almost every week. There are better ways to get affordable clothes that look good but last a long time, like second-hand clothes. Buying less and buying higher-quality clothes might help you more in the long run. Since good-quality clothes last for a long time, on average, clothes can last for 5 years, but with proper care, they can last for 15 years or more, and even if you don't like them anymore, you can sell them at a second-hand shop and get some money back. Especially since they are pricey, you will take more time to decide and probably use it more to get your money's worth.

Here are 3 small tips to make your clothes last longer

1. Better laundry habits (optional, link: [Laundry](#))
2. Actually read the garment care instructions and requirements (usually you can find the instructions on the tag or clothes).
3. Learn how to repair damaged clothes (example stains, small holes, etc).

To summarize this into points

- Fast fashion is the business model of replicating recent catwalk trends and high-fashion designs, mass-producing them at a low cost, and bringing them to retail stores quickly while demand is at its highest.
- Fast fashion is also called disposable fashion because it encourages a throw away consumer mentality.
- Buying cheaper clothes doesn't mean they will be cheaper in the long term.
- Buy what you need or truly want, not because it is trendy.
- Proper care will make your clothes last longer and save some money.

Source :

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